

Consent-based decision-making in social work

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ABSTRACT

Consent-based decision-making is a sociocratic method that has so far received little attention in the social work literature. Using an anonymised case example from disability support services, the paper demonstrates how consent, within a person-centred, non-directive support approach informed by Rogers, can provide immediate and pragmatic action guidance and contribute to de-escalation in conflict situations. The method is discussed as a concrete operationalisation of person-centredness, placed in relation to Nonviolent Communication (Rosenberg) and the RAID approach (Davies), and situated with regard to its potential applications in social group work, support planning, conflict mediation, and restorative justice processes.

KEYWORDS

consent-based decision-making · consent · sociocracy · social work · disability support · person-centred · non-directive · participation · nonviolent communication

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1 Introduction

In this paper I would like to present a method I have been using since 2016 in my work with people with learning disabilities and psychiatric diagnoses, both in day programmes and keywork in supported group living: consent-based decision-making (brief: consent). The case example I have chosen comes from the early phase of my work with consent in a social work context, at a time when I was using the method rather intuitively. Here I undertake the retrospective reflection and ask what role consent can play within a person-centred, non-directive support approach.

Consent-based decision-making has so far been largely absent from the social work literature. To my knowledge the only exception appears in a social work introduction to restorative justice, in which consent-based decision-making is described as a method that can be integrated into restorative justice practice (Früchtel & Halibrand, 2016, p. 119). Otherwise, consent is discussed primarily in the literature on organisational development and management, where it is typically introduced as one of several methods within the sociocratic management approach (Buck & Villines, 2017, pp. 159–173.; Strauch & Reijmer, 2018, pp. 33–56). More rarely, consent is also presented as a standalone method, as for example in Butler & Rothstein (1987).¹ Früchtel and Halibrand too introduce consent within the sociocratic framework (Früchtel & Halibrand, 2016, pp. 118–120). In reflecting on the method I will draw on an approach from one of social work's reference disciplines: psychology. Although connections to social work approaches and methods such as participation or social group work would be possible, I originally used the method as an action-oriented operationalisation of the person-centred approach,² and I want to examine it from precisely that perspective — the one that was originally

relevant to me — using a case example from 2016 from a disability support setting where I was working.

At that facility I had begun — in response to a resident population characterised throughout by significant challenging behaviours — implementing the RAID approach “a relentlessly positive approach in working with extreme behaviour” (Davies, 2000) in combination with Nonviolent Communication (following Rosenberg, 2015) and consent-based decision-making (following Butler & Rothstein, 1987). Mindfulness (Pfeifer-Schaupp, 2010) was a further approach used. It seems plausible that the combination of methods was significant, even though in what follows I focus my attention on consent-based decision-making.

At the time the case example took place, there was almost no literature on consent-based decision-making other than Butler and Rothstein (1987). I had previously encountered consent in an intentional community as a practised method of group decision-making, came to value it there, and transferred it from that lived experience into my social work practice. It was only in the years following the case example that further relevant literature appeared (Bockelbrink et al., 2020; Buck & Villines, 2017; Klein & Hughes, 2019; Rau & Koch-Gonzalez, 2018; Strauch & Reijmer, 2018), which I will draw on in my retrospective reflection.

2 Case example

Leo³ is 42 years old, has a moderate to severe cognitive impairment and limited communicative competence, becomes aggressive in psychotic phases, and has been marked by years of locked psychiatric inpatient treatment and psychotropic medication without any psychotherapeutic support. At the same time, he has built a reputation within the facility as someone who reliably takes part in daily life: he looks forward to shared activities, is socially

embedded in the residential home, and normally accompanies shared shopping trips with pleasure.

It is a morning in the residential home; the atmosphere is calm. As always, the group discusses the tasks for the morning. Group members can raise objections and we decide together which tasks we will tackle. On the day of the case example, a fellow resident proposes that Leo and she go shopping. Everyone agrees — everyone except Leo, who looks irritated and suddenly shouts “NO!” at the top of his voice, seemingly out of nowhere and without giving any further explanation.

The group is startled by the force of his reaction and, to some extent, frozen. I too am not immediately able to respond: this does not normally happen; Leo usually looks forward to the shopping trip. After a few mindful breaths I address Leo again and say: “You just said ‘no’ to our proposal. I’m interested in why you said ‘no’ and how we can find a solution together.” His reply is far less forceful, though still very loud and almost fearful: “My back hurts.” I respond: “Ah, your back hurts — that’s an important objection.” Leo replies now, relaxed and pleased: “Yes.” A sense of ease also spreads among the other residents. This shows me that I was able to help him name his tension and his objection, and that understanding Leo’s motivation helps everyone in this situation.

In the next step I consider how to handle the situation. It matters to me that everyone feels comfortable and that Leo is not excluded from the shared outing. As a resolution I make a proposal addressed primarily to Leo: “My proposal is that you come shopping with us, but that you don’t carry anything heavy. That way you can tell your fellow resident or me straight away if your back is hurting. We can then look at what is causing your back to hurt while shopping. We’ll do an experiment together to work out how you can take part without pain. Do you have any objections?” Leo says: “No, no objections — that’s really good.”

In the course of the shopping trip, through short, reflective conversations, we discover that Leo tends to walk faster and carry more than is good for him, building up emotional and physical tension in the process. We also arrive together at the insight that he has a tendency to bend over excessively and to carry heavy bags. Through these brief conversations he learns, in many small situations, to recognise his physical limits, and returns that morning without pain. In this way he has begun to recognise his body’s needs and also to verbalise his limits.

Over the following weeks and months it became clear to me through conversations with Leo that he had spent his whole life not refusing what was demanded of him, had a tendency not to be able to say “no”, and had been releasing the frustration that built up over many years or even decades through violent outbursts directed at those around him. His “no” was therefore, at that moment, a major breakthrough — a sign of courage and trust. Throughout his life he had frequently exceeded his physical limits, felt exploited and defenceless. For him, this “no” marked the beginning of a fundamental change that was only the start of a long journey towards greater self-confidence and self-determination.

3 Description of the method

In the case example I use consent-based decision-making not according to a rigid principle, but rather as an attitude, drawing situationally on various elements of the method within the frame of non-directive conversation facilitation.

3.1 Aims and function

Consent aims, instead of issuing directives, demands or instructions, to make proposals that are only adopted if none of those affected has a relevant objection (Strauch & Reijmer, 2018, pp. 36–40). In my practice, consent supplements a

person-centred, non-directive approach with a clearly described methodology offering immediate action guidance.⁴ Unlike therapeutic contexts, in social work action guidance is in many cases unavoidable, and in my observation leads many colleagues towards a directive approach. In the everyday reality of disability support services, as described in the case example, there are frequently practical constraints that make it difficult to work non-directively while still achieving necessary goals — such as a reliably structured daily routine. Consent supports me in pursuing a consistently non-directive approach in an action-oriented way even under considerable work pressure, while also not having to improvise entirely but instead keeping a rough methodological framework for conversations in the back of my mind — which I will now describe in more detail.

3.2 Process

The consent process is typically initiated by one person: this may be the social work practitioner or the client themselves. This person first clarifies “which problem needs to be solved” or articulates a perceived “tension” (Klein & Hughes, 2019, pp. 69, 92–93, 128–132, 137).⁵

Based on the tension, the person now formulates a proposal.⁶ Those present can briefly discuss the proposal and ask clarifying questions. Ideas for improving the proposal may also be raised, and the person can reconsider and modify their proposal (Klein & Hughes, 2019, pp. 137–141). If there are no objections to the proposal, “consent” is established at this point. If there are objections, these are now collected and noted down. One objection at a time is then integrated into the proposal through collective effort. The aim is primarily to make the proposal better than it was before (Klein & Hughes, 2019, p. 139). Sometimes not all objections can be integrated. If an objection is minor, the person who

raised it can often withdraw it. If it is a more significant objection, those present can decide whether it blocks the proposal. It is always important that a block is not an unsubstantiated veto but can be clearly and transparently justified (Buck & Villines, 2017, p. 301; Butler & Rothstein, 1987, pp. 30–31).

4 Reflection on the method in practice

In reflecting on the method in practice, I would first like to briefly analyse the case example and justify the choice of method, before going on to discuss particular features of consent in social work and briefly introducing various further applications.

4.1 Analysis of the case example

The case example opens with a proposal to the group: a shared shopping trip. Pragmatically, there is little discussion here — as is often done at this point in the consent process: everyone has a clear picture of what is being proposed. Leo’s objection comes loud and unexpectedly. Mindfulness and empathy are needed to give him the space to name his objection — namely his concern about back pain. The original proposal is now improved in consideration of Leo’s objection and is thereby acceptable to everyone. Leo’s objection sets in motion a significant and, for him, new development: he dares to say “no” and to articulate his needs, and he learns that there are alternative courses of action available to him that spare him the violent escalation to which he has been accustomed from his past.

In the case example I broadly follow the principles of non-directive counselling according to Rogers (2017, pp. 67–68):

- **Congruence / genuineness:** honest acknowledgement of my own being caught off guard, and transparent articulation of my

concern not to exclude Leo from the shared outing;

- **Unconditional positive regard:** Leo's concerns were taken seriously without reservation, neither dismissed nor trivialised;
- **Empathic understanding:** entering into Leo's distress and simply holding it there, with a brief paraphrase of his thoughts that created a visible sense of relief in him.

Above all, the resident is not confronted with "advice, admonitions, explanations and interpretations" (Weinberger, 2013, p. 22, own translation) but the process is steered in a solution-oriented direction. The use of the consent process enables immediate action guidance grounded in, and integrated with, the principles of non-directive counselling. Through proposals made by the practitioner, action impulses can be provided that the residents — if at all — would not be able to provide with the necessary speed, while at the same time there is unrestricted space for objections to be raised.

I selected the method and the action steps that followed in that moment intuitively. Were I to justify the choice retrospectively, I would do so along these lines: in the situation described, Leo's inclusion in the shared outing was important so that he would not be isolated. In a directive or authoritarian approach I would have told Leo to comply, possibly under announcement of consequences. This would most likely have felt to him like a threat, would have led sooner or later to a disruption of my relationship with him, and would probably have triggered a similar cycle of violence to those in other contexts in his past (see also Davies, 2000, p. 4). Empathically perceiving his situation and his needs (in the sense of Rosenberg, 2015, pp. 113–128) opens up a new course of action that works against a cycle of violence and seeks solution-oriented alternatives. Consent helps in this situation to create a satisfying

outcome for everyone involved. Leo appeared visibly relieved in and after the situation described. In conflicts with staff from other departments of the organisation, his new capacity led in the following months initially to an increase in conflicts, at the height of which Leo described a staff member as a "slave holder". In a shared reflection of the situation, that staff member was able to understand that Leo was developing a new capacity and that in certain situations he was overreacting. These overreactions are to be understood as the well-known "obnoxious stage" (Rosenberg, 2015, pp. 59–60) in the process of becoming aware of one's own needs. Both Leo and the staff members who found themselves in conflict with him during this phase learned that the "rebellious phase" was an important developmental step for Leo and that he would soon grow beyond it.

Returning to the case example as the beginning of a larger developmental process: drawing on methodical practice in that situation counteracted an impulsive reaction on the part of the practitioner. The methodological approach was able to de-escalate the situation, whereas an unreflective response to Leo's "no" would, in all likelihood, have led to escalation — at least that was the experience of colleagues in the past. The negotiation around his needs did, of course, take time — but how much more time would bypassing his needs have cost, with the resulting cycle of violence?

4.2 Consent in social work

Using this method in social work is, in my experience, characterised by a number of particular features that I would like to briefly describe.

When the client is the person who wishes to name a tension, this often requires — at least in the initial phase — empathic facilitation by the practitioner. In my experience, the first three basic steps of Nonviolent Communication are helpful here: first, describing the situation without evaluation

(Rosenberg, 2015, pp. 25–36), then naming the feelings this situation has evoked (Rosenberg, 2015, pp. 37–48), and finally identifying an underlying need (Rosenberg, 2015, pp. 49–66) from which a request can then be articulated (Rosenberg, 2015, pp. 67–90) — or, in the language of the consent method, the request would be called a “proposal”.

Balanced and restrained facilitation is also very helpful in the conversation following the formulation of the proposal. The facilitator may need to remind those present repeatedly that the conversation is not to become evaluative, demanding or directive. If the practitioner has made the proposal, it is often to be expected that the client — in many cases, given years of experience with directive practitioners — needs to find the trust that the proposal does not conceal a directive or instruction, but is rather a starting point for a conversation between equals.

Serious objections, which in other contexts are often justified with reference to the group’s constitution or vision, have a different quality in social work. Here one will primarily argue from laws or contracts and agreements — which may include care agreements or support plans. Sometimes common standards of conduct are grounds for serious objections, and in other cases something as mundane as the client’s bank balance, which makes a proposed course of action impossible. Above all, what matters here is that objections are principle-based and transparent — detailed, clearly reasoned and comprehensible.

Setting aside one’s own views and positions in the case of minor objections, or attending to sound arguments in the case of serious ones, is practice for both sides — for practitioners as much as for clients. The aim is to enter into a negotiation between equals, and this applies to both parties: neither the practitioner who patronises, nor the client who must act manipulatively to “push through” their

interests. Consent also offers social work a space for a shared learning process between practitioner and clients, even when not applied stringently but understood as an attitude more than as a method:

“Each person is capable of creating harmony, resilience, and responsiveness in themselves and in their environment. (...) small changes in your behavior and expectations can make a big difference (...) Function as if consent is the standard decision making” (Villines, in Buck & Villines, 2017, p. 239)

4.3 Examples of application

There are a wide range of possible applications for consent in social work, particularly in the context of participation and co-determination:

- in social group work, in supporting participation bodies in sheltered workshops or supported living, and in residents’ meetings in therapeutic shared living settings;
- in everyday situations where those involved are not of one mind; with some practice one then moves through the method unconsciously, both sides giving each other sufficient space to voice their concerns and to take them seriously;
- in support planning or other goal-setting processes, in which both practitioners and clients make proposals and raise concerns;⁷
- in conflict mediation meetings, in order to reach an agreement that everyone involved genuinely accepts;
- in team consultation for collaborative decision-making;
- integrated into social work restorative justice processes, as described by Früchtel and Halibrand (2016, p. 119).

5 Conclusion and outlook

The case example has demonstrated how consent-based decision-making can be used in a de-escalating way while at the same time enabling immediate and pragmatic action guidance within a person-centred support approach. Consent as a method could therefore indicate one possible path towards making a person-centred orientation in the spirit of Rogers (2017; see also Pörtner, 2015) workable for social work — precisely because it moves beyond the very open therapeutic frame that Rogers recommends and proposes clear steps through which sound decision-making can be purposefully implemented within a person-centred approach in the social work context. In some respects, consent can represent a concretisation of Rogers' person-centredness, in a similar way to Nonviolent Communication.

From the case example, however, no isolated effectiveness of consent can be derived. What becomes apparent is a plausible methodological function within a combined approach, in which RAID (Davies, 2000), Nonviolent Communication (Rosenberg, 2015), mindfulness and consent worked together — elements that retrospectively can barely be cleanly separated. Both a closer examination of this combination of methods and a look at further case examples would be needed in order to arrive at a more well-founded assessment. Evaluating the synergy of these approaches scientifically remains on my personal wish list.

Notes

- ¹ Butler and Rothstein use the term “formal consensus” but describe essentially the same procedure as the consent method.
- ² In the terminology and approach of the person-centred, non-directive approach I draw on Rogers (2017), with operationalisation for the social work context through Weinberger (2013).
- ³ The case example is anonymised: the name has been

changed, and personal and facility-related details have been altered in such a way that identification is not possible.

- ⁴ Rogers did not wish person-centredness to be understood as a method or technique, which has been received as not unproblematic in both scholarship and practice (Weinberger, 2013, p. 41, own translation). With Nonviolent Communication, Rosenberg — as a student of Rogers — implemented Rogers' work methodologically (Rosenberg, 2015, pp. 113, 199–200). In a similar sense to Nonviolent Communication, consent integrates as a method of social work into a person-centred approach.
- ⁵ For the articulation of a tension in work with the people social work is addressed to, in my experience the first three steps of Nonviolent Communication are helpful; see below in the section “Consent in social work”.
- ⁶ This step is analogous to the formulation of a request in Nonviolent Communication (Rosenberg, 2015, pp. 67–90).
- ⁷ “When in a support planning meeting a specific social-pedagogical provision is professionally enforced in the presence of the young person and against their agreement, this is an expression of the power relations prevailing there. Whether this (...) was, in perspective, an appropriate and helpful decision will only (...) become apparent later” (Kessl, 2021, p. 27, own translation).

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